

Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting Potential Assessment At Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya, Shrigonda

Vaibhavi K. Sable

Assistant Professor, Department of Geography, Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya, Shrigonda

Corresponding Author – Vaibhavi K. Sable

DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.19951517

Abstract:

Water scarcity has become a major environmental concern in semi-arid regions of India due to increasing population, urbanization, and excessive groundwater extraction. Rooftop rainwater harvesting (RTRWH) is considered an effective and sustainable technique for water conservation, especially in institutional campuses that possess large rooftop areas. The present study assesses the rooftop rainwater harvesting potential of Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya located in Shrigonda, Ahmednagar district, Maharashtra. Rooftop areas of selected buildings were identified and digitized using Google Earth Pro and QGIS software. Annual rainfall data for the period 2005–2014 were collected from the Ahmednagar District Gazetteer. The potential volume of harvested rainwater was estimated using the standard formula $Q=C \times I \times A$, where Q represents harvestable rainwater, C denotes runoff coefficient, I represent rainfall, and A indicates rooftop catchment area. The results reveal that the selected buildings within the campus have the potential to harvest approximately 1.65 million litres of rainwater annually. Among the buildings studied, B Wing and the Girls' Hostel show the highest harvesting potential due to their larger rooftop areas. The study highlights that implementing rooftop rainwater harvesting in the college campus can significantly contribute to water conservation and sustainable water management in semi-arid regions.

Keywords: Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting, Runoff Coefficient, Catchment Area

Introduction:

Water scarcity has emerged as one of the most critical environmental and socio-economic challenges in India over the past few decades. Rapid population growth, urban expansion, industrialization, and intensive groundwater extraction have significantly increased domestic water demand while simultaneously reducing freshwater availability (Kumar, 2004). Urban and semi-urban regions in particular are experiencing declining per capita water availability and increasing inequity in water distribution, especially during drought years (Kumar, 2004). Nearly 80% of rural domestic needs and about 50% of urban water requirements in India depend on groundwater sources, many of which are facing depletion and quality deterioration due to

over-extraction and contamination (Kumar, 2004).

In response to these challenges, rooftop rainwater harvesting (RWH) has been widely promoted as a sustainable and decentralized water management strategy. India has a long tradition of rainwater harvesting practices, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, where communities historically depended on harvested rainwater for domestic and agricultural needs (Kumar, 2004). However, modernization and the expansion of centralized piped water supply systems led to a decline in traditional harvesting practices (Kumar, 2004). In recent years, due to increasing water stress and groundwater depletion, rooftop rainwater harvesting systems (RWHS) have

regained attention as a viable supplementary water source.

Rooftop rainwater harvesting (RTRWH) systems are generally more efficient in regions that experience high rainfall intensity along with well-distributed precipitation throughout the year, as such climatic conditions enhance the reliability and volume of harvested water (Kumar, 2004). Public institutions, particularly large government establishments, often possess extensive rooftop areas, making them strategically suitable for implementing effective RTRWH systems (Adugna et al., 2018). These institutions typically operate under a centralized administrative framework and have comparatively better access to financial resources, which facilitates smoother planning, installation, and maintenance of rainwater harvesting infrastructure.

Moreover, as recognized and trusted public entities, universities and government institutions can play a demonstrative role by promoting confidence in rooftop rainwater harvesting among local communities and other organizations. Their adoption of such systems can encourage wider acceptance and replication. Despite these advantages, limited research and practical initiatives have been reported regarding rooftop rainwater harvesting potential in government buildings, especially at the university or institutional scale (Saedi & Goodarzi, 2020).

Within a university setting, campus management practices significantly influence the quality of life of a large population, including students, faculty, and staff. The presence of well-maintained green spaces and landscaped areas contributes to a strong sense of community and represents an important structural and aesthetic feature of campus environments (Speake et al., 2013). Green infrastructure is also a key factor considered by students during university selection processes. Survey findings indicate that a considerable proportion of students prefer

campuses with substantial green areas, as these spaces help alleviate academic stress and improve overall well-being (Seitz et al., 2013). Furthermore, research conducted among undergraduate students suggests that exposure to campus green spaces positively influences academic performance and overall educational outcomes (McFarland et al., 2008).

Rooftop rainwater harvesting involves the collection of rainwater from building roofs, its conveyance through gutters and downpipes, filtration to remove debris and suspended particles, and storage in tanks for later use (IJRASET, 2023). The main objective of the present study is to estimate the rooftop rainwater harvesting potential of selected buildings in Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya campus, Shrigonda.

Study Area:

Shrigonda is a semi-urban town located in the Ahmednagar district of Maharashtra, India. It lies in the western part of the Deccan Plateau and forms part of the semi-arid climatic region of the state. Geographically, Shrigonda is situated between approximately 18°36' to 18°40' North latitude and 74°40' to 74°45' East longitude. The town experiences a tropical semi-arid climate characterized by hot summers, moderate monsoon rainfall, and mild winters.

The average annual rainfall in the region ranges between 450 mm and 650 mm, primarily received during the southwest monsoon season (June to September). However, rainfall variability is relatively high, and occasional drought conditions are common. Such climatic characteristics make water resource management a critical issue for the region. Groundwater serves as the primary source of domestic and agricultural water supply, but declining water tables and seasonal shortages have increased the need for

alternative water conservation strategies, including rooftop rainwater harvesting.

Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya is a prominent higher educational institution located in Shrigonda town. The campus covers a considerable land area of 16.5 acres comprising academic buildings, administrative blocks, laboratories, library facilities, and open green spaces. The built-up infrastructure includes multiple RCC-roofed buildings, which provide substantial rooftop catchment area suitable for rainwater harvesting. (Fig 2)

The campus environment includes landscaped gardens and green spaces that enhance ecological balance and improve the quality of campus life. These green areas require regular water supply for maintenance, especially during dry months.

Fig 1- Campus of Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya

Fig 2- Buildings Selected for study from Campus.

Methodology:

1. Sample Selection and Data collection: For the present study, buildings with suitable rooftop areas for rainwater harvesting were selected within the college campus. Figure 2 and Table 3 show the buildings selected for analysis. Using remote sensing and GIS techniques, the rooftop areas of the selected buildings were digitized using Google Earth Pro satellite imagery. The rooftop areas were measured in square meters. Rainfall data for Shrigonda taluka were collected from the Ahmednagar District Gazetteer. For the present analysis, annual rainfall data for the period **2005–2014** were used to calculate the average annual rainfall.

All statistical calculations were performed using **Microsoft Excel**, while maps were prepared using **QGIS open-source software** by digitizing the college campus layout.

2. Estimation of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting Potential: The rooftop rainwater harvesting potential was calculated using the following formula:

$$Q = C \times I \times A$$

Where:

Q = Quantity of harvested rainwater (litres per year)

C = Runoff coefficient

I = Annual rainfall (mm)

A = Rooftop catchment area (m²) (Anchan & Prasad, 2021).

Table 1 - Runoff coefficient values for various roof types.

Sl. No.	Type of roof	Runoff coefficient
1	Galvanized iron sheet	0.90
2	Asbestos sheet	0.80
3	Tiled roof	0.75
4	Concrete roof	0.70

Source: *Water harvesting. A manual for design & construction of water harvesting schemes for plant production (1991), Anchan & Prasad, (2021).*

Table 1 presents the runoff coefficient values for four common roofing materials used for construction. The runoff coefficient depends on the type of roofing material used in the building.

For the present study, the buildings mainly consist of concrete roofs and galvanized iron sheet roofs, and therefore the corresponding runoff coefficients were used.

Result and discussion:

1. Rainfall Statistics:

Table 2- Annual Rainfall of Shrigonda (2005-2014)

Taluka	Year	Rainfall (mm)
Shrigonda	2005	484
	2006	505
	2007	675
	2008	448
	2009	499
	2010	710
	2011	326
	2012	258
	2013	777
	2014	268
Average		448.6

Fig 3- Annual Rainfall of Shrigonda 2005-2014

Table 2 shows the annual rainfall data for Shrigonda taluka for the period **2005–2014**. The rainfall varies significantly from year to year,

indicating variability in precipitation in the region.

The average annual rainfall for Shrigonda during the study period was approximately **448.6 mm**, indicating relatively low rainfall conditions typical of semi-arid regions. This highlights the importance of implementing rainwater harvesting techniques to conserve available water resources.

Catchment Area:

Fig 4- Rooftop Catchment Area of According to Building

The fig 4 pie chart represents the area of the selected building rooftop for rainwater

harvesting. The rooftop catchment area of selected buildings was measured using Google Earth Pro. The results show that larger buildings have greater rooftop areas and therefore higher rainwater harvesting potential.

Among the selected buildings, the **Girls' Hostel and B Wing buildings have the largest rooftop areas**, followed by the C Wing and the Main Administrative Building. Buildings with larger rooftop areas contribute significantly to the total harvested rainwater potential.

Potential Harvested Water:

Table 3 – Building wise Rooftop Type, Area, Runoff Coefficient and Discharge

Building Name	Roof Type	A- Roof top catchment Area m ²	C-Runoff Coefficient	I - Intensity of Rainfall mm	Q - Discharge from Roof (m ³ s) / Liters
Main Administrative Building	Concrete Roof	783	0.7	448.6	245877.66
B Wing	Galvanized Iron Sheet	1086	0.9	448.6	438461.64
C Wing	Concrete Roof	869	0.7	448.6	272883.38
Library	Concrete Roof	300.4	0.7	448.6	94331.608
MCVC	Galvanized Iron Sheet	134	0.9	448.6	54101.16
Girls Hostel	Concrete Roof	1025	0.7	448.6	321870.5
Gymkhana	Galvanized Iron Sheet	555	0.9	448.6	224075.7
Total potential water					1651601.648

Fig 5- Building wise Rooftop Discharge

The rooftop rainwater harvesting potential was calculated for each building based on rooftop area, rainfall, and runoff coefficient.

The results show that buildings with larger rooftop areas generate greater volumes of harvested rainwater. The B Wing and Girls' Hostel buildings contribute the highest harvesting potential, while the MCVC building has the lowest potential due to its smaller rooftop area.

The total estimated rainwater harvesting potential of the selected campus buildings is approximately 1,651,601 litres per year. (Table 3)

This indicates that a significant amount of rainwater can be captured and utilized through the installation of a rooftop rainwater harvesting system in the college campus.

Conclusion:

The present study assessed the rooftop rainwater harvesting potential of selected buildings within the Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya campus in Shrigonda. Using rainfall data, rooftop catchment area measurements, and runoff coefficients, the study estimated the potential volume of harvestable rainwater.

The analysis revealed that the campus buildings possess considerable potential for rainwater harvesting due to their large rooftop areas. Based on the average annual rainfall of approximately 448.6 mm, the total rooftop rainwater harvesting potential of the selected buildings was estimated to be about 1.65 million litres per year.

Among the buildings studied, B Wing and the Girls' Hostel buildings contribute the highest harvesting potential, while the MCVC building contributes the least due to its smaller catchment area. The results demonstrate that institutional campuses with large building structures provide excellent opportunities for implementing rooftop rainwater harvesting systems.

Implementing such a system at Shri Chhatrapati Shivaji Mahavidyalaya would help reduce dependence on groundwater sources, support sustainable water management, and promote environmental awareness among students and the local community. Educational institutions can play an important role in demonstrating sustainable water conservation practices in semi-arid regions.

References:

1. Adugna, D., Jensen, M., Lemma, B., & Gebrie, G. S. (2018). Assessing the potential for rooftop rainwater harvesting from large public institutions. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 15(2), 336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15020336>
2. Ahmednagar District Gazetteer. (n.d.). *Ahmednagar district gazetteer*. Government of Maharashtra.
3. Anchan, S. S., & Prasad, H. C. S. (2021). Feasibility of rooftop rainwater harvesting potential: A case study of a South Indian university. *Cleaner Engineering and Technology*, 4, 100206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clet.2021.100206>
4. IJRASET. (2023). Design of rainwater harvesting system at MPCOE campus. *International Journal for Research in Applied Science & Engineering Technology*, 11(7), 47–55. <https://doi.org/10.22214/ijraset.2023.54163>
5. Kumar, M. D. (2004). Roof water harvesting for domestic water security: Who gains and who loses? *Water International*, 29(1), 43–53.
6. McFarland, A. L., Waliczek, T. M., & Zajicek, J. M. (2008). The relationship between student use of campus green spaces and perceptions of quality of life. *Hort Technology*, 18(2), 232–238. <https://doi.org/10.21273/HORTTECH.18.2.232>
7. Saeedi, I., & Goodarzi, M. (2020). Rainwater harvesting system: A sustainable method for landscape development in semiarid regions, the case of Malayer University campus in Iran. *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, 22(2), 1579–1598. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-018-0218-8>

8. Seitz, C., Reese, M., Strack, R., Frantz, W., & West, S. B. (2014). Identifying and improving green spaces on a college campus: A photovoice study. *Ecopsychology*, 6(2), 98–108. <https://doi.org/10.1089/eco.2013.0112>
9. Speake, J., Edmondson, S., & Nawaz, H. (2013). Everyday encounters with nature: Students' perceptions and use of university campus green spaces. *Journal of Studies and Research in Human Geography*, 7(1), 21–31.